

Paper 27

**SELECTIVITY AND MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE:
AN EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION OF SELECTED
EQUITY DIVERSIFIED SCHEMES IN INDIA**

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Abstract

The mutual fund industry in India has grown to a remarkable extent in the recent decade, therefore performance evaluation is potentially important. The present paper is an empirical study of investment performance of 52 selected Indian equity diversified mutual fund (growth) schemes for the period from 1st April 2009 to 31st March 2019. The performance is evaluated in terms of rate of return, risk and diversification and stock selectivity skills of fund managers. Measures such as Jensen and Fama is used in the analysis of stock selection skills of fund managers. Results shows that about 65% of the mutual fund schemes were able to beat the benchmark markets. All the schemes under study were relatively exposed to less risk than the market, however with high degree of volatility. A majority of the funds were reasonably diversified. Empirical evidence also suggests that fund managers of some of the sample mutual fund schemes were engaged in micro forecasting (or stock selection) as the alpha values in about 38% of the schemes were found to be positive and statistically significant.

Keywords: Return, Risk, Jensen alpha, Fama's measure, Selectivity

1. INTRODUCTION

Economic liberalization and globalization have brought a fervent environment for the medium and small investors in India. With emphasis on increase in domestic savings and improvement in deployment of investment through markets, the need and scope for mutual fund operation has increased tremendously. The mutual fund industry, which began its journey in India with the setting up of the Unit Trust of India in 1964 has grown several folds in terms of size and operations during the past five decades of its existence. There has been substantial growth in terms of assets under management, variety of investment schemes. From a single player the number of players has increased to 44 with managed assets of Rs.23,79,584 crore as on 31st March 2019.

The evaluation of performance of mutual funds and the identification of successful fund managers are of great interest to both investors and academics. Two possible methods are

presumed to be used by fund managers for generating superior performance are identified as 'stock selection' and market timing. Stock selection involve micro forecasting of the price movements of the individual stocks relative to the market and identification of the individual stocks that are under or over valued relative to the equities in general. Market timing skills imply assessing correctly the direction of the market, whether bull or bear, and positioning the portfolios accordingly. These two abilities constitute the major components of active management skills of fund managers. From an academic perspective, the existence (and persistence) of mutual fund managerial ability will imply a rejection of the efficient market hypothesis.

The present paper evaluates the performance of mutual fund schemes through risk-return analysis and also evaluates the stock selection ability of fund managers of selected equity diversified schemes in India. The study contributes to the literature by providing evidence on stock selection ability of fund managers of equity diversified mutual funds in India.

2. Objectives of the Study

1. To evaluate the performance of selected mutual fund schemes on the basis of risk-return parameters.
2. To evaluate the stock selection skills of the fund managers of equity diversified mutual fund schemes in India.

3. Selection of Schemes and Database description

The study uses a sample of 52 equity diversified open ended mutual fund schemes (regular plan with growth option) of various fund houses. The period of the study is for 10 years form 1st April 2009 to 31st March 2019. The sample of 52 schemes has been drawn from the population of Indian equity diversified mutual fund schemes which invests in variety of equity financial assets and which are not sector specific. The schemes may be active or passive in nature. The study has focused on only the active equity diversified schemes for which the stock selection ability is relevant. Mutual fund schemes have both the dividend and growth options, as well as direct and regular scheme. The study has focused on only the regular schemes with growth option.

The mutual fund schemes selected are of varied size and are based on different benchmarks. Schemes launched before April 2009 are included in the study period. The choice of the sample is largely based upon the availability of the necessary data. Only those equity schemes where the continuous data was available for all the 10 years of study period were included in the sample.

Daily net asset values (NAVs) obtained from the official website of the association of mutual funds in India (www.amfiindia.com) has been used for the purpose of the study. NSE Total return index is used as a benchmark. Total returns index reflects the returns on the index arising from (a) constituent stock price movements and (b) dividend receipts from constituent index stocks. From February 2018 all the mutual funds have been mandated to use Total return index as the new benchmark. Data on NSE Total return index and 91 day Treasury bills is collected from NSE website and RBI website respectively.

Table 1: Description of Sample Mutual Fund Schemes and Benchmark Index

	Name of the Scheme	Sub Category	Type	Benchmark	Launch Date
1	Principal Multi Cap Growth Fund(G)	Equity - Multi Cap Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	3-Oct-00
2	DSP Equity Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - Multi Cap Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	4-Apr-97
3	Franklin India Equity Fund(G)	Equity - Multi Cap Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	29-Sep-94
4	HDFC Equity Fund(G)	Equity - Multi Cap Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	8-Dec-94
5	LIC MF Multi Cap Fund(G)	Equity - Multi Cap Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	16-Apr-98
6	Quant Active Fund(G)	Equity - Multi Cap Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 500	19-Feb-01
7	Kotak India EQ Contra Fund(G)	Equity - Contra Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 100 - TRI	2-Jun-05
8	Principal Dividend Yield Fund(G)	Equity - Dividend Yield Fund	Open ended	NIFTY DIV OPPTS 50 - TRI	6-Sep-04
9	Templeton India Equity Income Fund (G)	Equity - Dividend Yield Fund	Open ended	NIFTY DIV OPPTS 50	22-Mar-06
10	UTI Dividend Yield Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - Dividend Yield Fund	Open ended	NIFTY DIV OPPTS 50 - TRI	11-Apr-05

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1 1	Aditya Birla SL Dividend Yield Fund(G)	Equity - Dividend Yield Fund	Open ended	NIFTY DIV OPPS 50 - TRI	23-Jan-03
1 2	Canara Rob Emerg Equities Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - Large & Mid Cap Fund	Open ended	Nifty LargeMidcap 250 Index - TRI	11-Feb-05
1 3	DSP Equity Opportunities Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - Large & Mid Cap Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	11-Mar-00
1 4	Kotak Equity Opp Fund(G)	Equity - Large & Mid Cap Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 200 - TRI	10-Sep-04
1 5	Sundaram Large and Mid Cap Fund(G)	Equity - Large & Mid Cap Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 200 - TRI	10-Jan-07
1 6	Principal Emerging Bluechip Fund(G)	Equity - Large & Mid Cap Fund	Open ended	Nifty LargeMidcap 250 Index - TRI	22-Sep-08
1 7	Franklin India Equity Advantage Fund (G)	Equity - Large & Mid Cap Fund	Open ended	Nifty LargeMidcap 250 Index	17-Jan-05
1 8	ICICI Pru Large & Mid Cap Fund(G)	Equity - Large & Mid Cap Fund	Open ended	Nifty LargeMidcap 250 Index - TRI	1-Jun-98
1 9	SBI Large & Midcap Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - Large & Mid Cap Fund	Open ended	Nifty LargeMidcap 250 Index - TRI	1-Jan-93
2 0	UTI Core Equity Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - Large & Mid Cap Fund	Open ended	Nifty LargeMidcap 250 Index - TRI	20-May-09
2 1	Quant Large & Mid Cap Fund(G)	Equity - Large & Mid Cap Fund	Open	Nifty LargeMidcap 250	20-Nov-06

			ende d	Index	
2 2 2	Mirae Asset Large Cap Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - Large Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	NIFTY 100 - TRI	11-Feb-08
2 3	ICICI PruBluechip Fund(G)	Equity - Large Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	NIFTY 100 - TRI	8-Apr-08
2 4	Aditya Birla SL Frontline Equity Fund (G)	Equity - Large Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	NIFTY 50 - TRI	23-Sep-02
2 5	HDFC Top 100 Fund(G)	Equity - Large Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	NIFTY 100 - TRI	19-Aug-96
2 6	Franklin India Bluechip Fund(G)	Equity - Large Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	NIFTY 100 - TRI	1-Dec-93
2 7	HSBC Large Cap Equity Fund(G)	Equity - Large Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	NIFTY 50 - TRI	14-Nov-02
2 8	LIC MF Large Cap Fund(G)	Equity - Large Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	NIFTY 100 - TRI	1-Sep-94
2 9	DSP Midcap Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - Mid Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Midcap 100 - TRI	29-Sep-06
3 0	HDFC Mid-Cap Opportunities Fund(G)	Equity - Mid Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Midcap 100 - TRI	7-May-07
3 1	Kotak Emerging Equity Scheme(G)	Equity - Mid Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Midcap 100 - TRI	12-Feb-07
3	Aditya Birla SL Midcap	Equity - Mid Cap	Ope	Nifty Midcap 100	9-Sep-02

2	Fund(G)	Fund	n ende d	- TRI	
3 3	ICICI Pru Midcap Fund(G)	Equity - Mid Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Midcap 150 - TRI	6-Sep-04
3 4	Invesco India Midcap Fund(G)	Equity - Mid Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Midcap 100 - TRI	2-Jan-03
3 5	UTI Mid Cap Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - Mid Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Midcap 150 - TRI	21-Feb-05
3 6	SBI Magnum Midcap Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - Mid Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Midcap 150 - TRI	15-Jun-94
3 7	Tata Mid Cap Growth Fund(G)	Equity - Mid Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Midcap 100 - TRI	12-Feb-01
3 8	Quant Mid Cap Fund(G)	Equity - Mid Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Midcap 150	5-Sep-94
3 9	Taurus Discovery (Midcap) Fund-Reg (G)	Equity - Mid Cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Midcap 100 - TRI	9-Apr-07
4 0	Aditya Birla SL Small Cap Fund(G)	Equity - Small cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Smallcap 100 - TRI	16-Nov-05
4 1	Franklin India Smaller Cos Fund(G)	Equity - Small cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Smallcap 250 - TRI	30-Dec-04
4 2	Kotak Small Cap Fund(G)	Equity - Small cap Fund	Ope n ende d	Nifty Smallcap 50 - TRI	23-Sep-96

43	Quant Small Cap Fund(G)	Equity - Small cap Fund	Open ended	Nifty 250 Smallcap	23-Aug-07
44	ICICI PruSmallcap Fund(G)	Equity - Small cap Fund	Open ended	Nifty 250 - TRI Smallcap	27-Nov-06
45	DSP Tax Saver Fund-Reg(G)	Equity - ELSS	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	11-Dec-12
46	ICICI Pru LT Equity Fund (Tax Saving) (G)	Equity - ELSS	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	1-Jan-96
47	Principal Tax Savings Fund	Equity - ELSS	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	10-Apr-94
48	Franklin India Taxshield(G)	Equity - ELSS	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	30-Sep-05
49	Kotak Tax Saver Scheme(G)	Equity - ELSS	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	31-Mar-96
50	HDFC TaxSaver(G)	Equity - ELSS	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	10-Apr-94
51	Quant Tax Plan(G)	Equity - ELSS	Open ended	NIFTY 50 - TRI	16-Dec-93
52	HDFC Capital Builder Value Fund(G)	Equity - Value Fund	Open ended	NIFTY 500 - TRI	16-Dec-93

4. Research Methodology

Return and Risk of selected equity schemes

Fund returns are assumed to be continuously compounded and are calculated as follows:

The daily log returns are computed on the basis of the Net asset values of different schemes and returns on the market index are calculated on the basis of various index values on the respective date for the 10 years.

The log returns from a mutual fund scheme (R_{pt}) at time t , is as follows

p^t

L_n

n^t

C

$=$

$\$$

Where σ_p is the total risk of the scheme portfolio.

The total risk of the market line portfolio is:

m

=

p

)		x))		
Principal Multi Cap Growth Fund(G)	0.0654	36	0.0626	1.0710	1.0709	0.9262	0.9625
DSP Equity Fund-Reg(G)	0.0661	35	0.0626	1.0388	1.0709	0.9001	0.9202
Franklin India Equity Fund(G)	0.0690	26	0.0626	0.9416	1.0709	0.9321	0.8489
HDFC Equity Fund(G)	0.0741	18	0.0626	1.1327	1.0709	0.9009	1.0039
LIC MF Multi Cap Fund(G)	0.0475	49	0.0632	1.1352	1.0759	0.8855	0.9929
Quant Active Fund(G)	0.0675	31	0.0628	1.0953	1.0702	0.5924	0.7877
Kotak India EQ Contra Fund(G)	0.0639	39	0.0627	0.9834	1.0950	0.9216	0.8621
Principal Dividend Yield Fund(G)	0.0640	38	0.0705	0.9997	1.0227	0.8535	0.9031
Templeton India Equity Income Fund (G)	0.0664	32	0.0706	0.9035	1.0229	0.6573	0.7161
UTI Dividend Yield Fund-Reg(G)	0.0596	45	0.0705	0.9157	1.0227	0.8518	0.8263
Aditya Birla SL Dividend Yield Fund(G)	0.0609	43	0.0705	0.9253	1.0227	0.8047	0.8115
Canara Rob Emerg Equities Fund-Reg(G)	0.1012	1	0.0711	1.0256	1.0823	0.8255	0.8610
DSP Equity Opportunities Fund-Reg(G)	0.0691	25	0.0626	1.0093	1.0709	0.9315	0.9097
Kotak Equity Opp Fund(G)	0.0682	30	0.0621	1.0282	1.0850	0.9425	0.9200

Sundaram Large and Mid Cap Fund(G)	0.063 1	41	0.062 1	1.0375	1.0850	0.8399	0.8763
Principal Emerging Bluechip Fund(G)	0.088 7	5	0.071 1	1.0799	1.0823	0.9051	0.9492
Franklin India Equity Advantage Fund (G)	0.069 2	24	0.071 1	1.0165	1.0829	0.9095	0.8953
ICICI Pru Large & Mid Cap Fund(G)	0.060 3	44	0.071 1	0.9950	1.0823	0.8618	0.8535
SBI Large & Midcap Fund-Reg(G)	0.069 5	23	0.071 5	1.0030	1.0792	0.9148	0.8889
UTI Core Equity Fund-Reg(G)	0.027 8	52	0.071 2	1.6975	1.0803	0.3089	0.8734
Quant Large & Mid Cap Fund(G)	0.066 3	33	0.071 3	1.9343	1.0761	0.1856	0.7745
Mirae Asset Large Cap Fund-Reg(G)	0.083 0	8	0.062 7	1.0381	1.0950	0.9470	0.9225
ICICI PruBluechip Fund(G)	0.069 7	22	0.062 7	1.0009	1.0950	0.9469	0.8895
Aditya Birla SL Frontline Equity Fund (G)	0.068 6	28	0.059 2	1.0117	1.0985	0.9517	0.8985
HDFC Top 100 Fund(G)	0.068 4	29	0.062 7	1.1195	1.0950	0.9255	0.9835
Franklin India Bluechip Fund(G)	0.061 8	42	0.062 7	0.9500	1.0950	0.9415	0.8417
HSBC Large Cap Equity Fund(G)	0.050 5	48	0.059 2	1.0151	1.0985	0.9348	0.8934
LIC MF Large Cap Fund(G)	0.055 9	46	0.063 3	1.0932	1.0996	0.8977	0.9419
DSP Midcap Fund-Reg(G)	0.086 7	6	0.072 8	1.0746	1.1748	0.8678	0.8521
HDFC Mid-Cap Opportunities Fund(G)	0.091 5	2	0.073 2	0.9397	1.1747	0.6736	0.6565
Kotak Emerging Equity	0.079	12	0.073	0.9747	1.1747	0.8756	0.7764

Scheme(G)	4		2				
Aditya Birla SL Midcap Fund(G)	0.0773	15	0.0732	1.0826	1.1747	0.0773	0.0732
ICICI Pru Midcap Fund(G)	0.0791	13	0.0800	1.0082	1.1561	0.8586	0.8081
Invesco India Midcap Fund(G)	0.0893	4	0.0732	0.9647	1.1747	0.8530	0.7584
UTI Mid Cap Fund-Reg(G)	0.0844	7	0.0800	1.0573	1.1561	0.9079	0.8714
SBI Magnum Midcap Fund-Reg(G)	0.0819	9	0.0805	1.0792	1.1508	0.8389	0.8589
Tata Mid Cap Growth Fund(G)	0.0802	11	0.0732	1.0194	1.1747	0.8745	0.8115
Quant Mid Cap Fund(G)	0.0375	50	0.0802	0.6134	1.1457	0.2996	0.2930
Taurus Discovery (Midcap) Fund-Reg (G)	0.0741	19	0.0732	1.1635	1.1747	0.8921	0.9355
Aditya Birla SL Small Cap Fund(G)	0.0816	10	0.0629	1.0648	1.3328	0.8380	0.7313
Franklin India Smaller Cos Fund(G)	0.0913	3	0.0684	1.0055	1.2350	0.8490	0.7502
Kotak Small Cap Fund(G)	0.0774	14	0.0511	1.0443	1.4863	0.8030	0.6296
Quant Small Cap Fund(G)	0.0330	51	0.0687	1.2126	1.2340	0.0098	0.0974
ICICI PruSmallcap Fund(G)	0.0643	37	0.0698	0.8208	1.2568	0.6117	0.5108
DSP Tax Saver Fund-Reg(G)	0.0736	20	0.0626	0.9977	1.0709	0.9381	0.9023
ICICI Pru LT Equity Fund (Tax Saving) (G)	0.0764	16	0.0626	0.9146	1.0709	0.8915	0.8063
Principal Tax Savings Fund	0.0661	34	0.0626	1.0799	1.0709	0.9272	0.9710

Franklin India Taxshield(G)	0.071 6	21	0.062 6	0.9316	1.0709	0.9300	0.8389
Kotak Tax Saver Scheme(G)	0.063 5	40	0.062 6	1.0379	1.0709	0.9518	0.9455
HDFC TaxSaver(G)	0.068 7	27	0.062 6	1.0139	1.0709	0.8859	0.8911
Quant Tax Plan(G)	0.052 5	47	0.059 3	1.0469	1.1013	0.5415	0.6995
HDFC Capital Builder Value Fund(G)	0.075 8	17	0.062 6	0.9431	1.0709	0.9094	0.8398

Return and Risk Analysis

The average daily return along with the ranking based on this return is presented in Table 2. All the schemes have recorded positive average daily return values during the study period. A close look at the Table 2 indicates that out of the total 52 schemes 34 schemes (65%) have outperformed the market by earning returns higher than the market/benchmark returns, whereas 18 schemes have under performed the market index. The risk free return 0.0193 for the study period and all the schemes have earned returns greater than the risk free rate of return.

The ranking pattern based on return statistics shows that Canara Robeco Emerging Equity Fund (Equity Large & Mid-cap fund), HDFC Mid-Cap Opportunities Fund(G) (Mid-cap), Franklin India Smaller companies Fund (Small-Cap) have got the top 1st, 2nd and 3rd ranks respectively.

The **total risk** (Standard deviation) incorporates systematic and unsystematic risk (beta). The standard deviation of all the schemes lies between 1.9343 (Quant Large & Mid Cap Fund) and 0.6134 (Quant Mid Cap Fund). Taking the Scheme wise risk in terms of **Standard deviation** only 8 schemes (15%) have undertaken higher risk than the market whereas all other funds analysed in this study have lower risk compared to market in general.

Positive value of **beta** in the case of all the mutual fund schemes indicates that the fund return closely follows the market return. All the schemes except one scheme that is HDFC Equity Fund have recorded beta less than 1 indicating holding of relatively less risky portfolio than the market portfolio. However, majority of the schemes are highly volatile as their betas have high value, 38 schemes have recorded a beta of more than 0.8.

Diversification: Co-efficient of determination (R^2)

Table 2 also shows the values of co-efficient of determination for each of the 52 equity diversified schemes, when measured with the market index, 42 out of 52 schemes i.e about 81% of the sampled funds have recorded R^2 value of more than 0.8 which indicates that these schemes have reasonably exploited the diversification strategy in forming their portfolio. The highest R^2 value was found in Kotak Tax saver scheme (0.9518) and the lowest R^2 value was found in Quant Small Cap fund (0.00981).

Sl. no	Scheme	Jensen Measure				Fama's measure					
		Jensen Alpha	Rank	t-Stat	P-value	Rf	Compensation for systematic risk	Compensation for inadequate diversification	Net superior returns	Average (Fund)	Rank (Fama net selectivity)
1	Principal Multi Cap Growth Fund(G)	0.00438	39	0.7461	0.4557	0.0193	0.0401	0.0032	0.0028	0.0654	35
2	DSP Equity Fund-Reg(G)	0.00698	32	1.0532	0.2924	0.0193	0.039	0.003	0.0048	0.0661	30
3	Franklin India Equity Fund(G)	0.013 *	20	2.6245	0.0087	0.0193	0.0404	-0.0023	0.0117	0.069	18
4	HDFC Equity Fund(G)	0.01133 *	23	0.1156	-0.0028	0.0193	0.039	0.0068	0.009	0.0741	21
5	LIC MF Multi Cap Fund(G)	-0.0153	51	-1.969	0.0491	0.0193	0.0389	0.0075	-0.0181	0.0475	49
6	Quant Active	0.0139	18	0.9854	0.3245	0.0193	0.0258	0.0188	0.0037	0.0675	32

	Fund(G)										
7	Kotak India EQ Contra Fund(G)	0.0072	31	1.2945	0.1956	0.0193	0.04	-0.001	0.0056	0.0639	27
8	Principal Dividend Yield Fund(G)	0.0016	46	-0.206	0.8366	0.0193	0.0438	0.0064	0.0054	0.064	43
9	Templeton India Equity Income Fund(G)	0.0104	26	1.4834	0.1381	0.0193	0.0337	0.0116	0.0018	0.0664	37
10	UTI Dividend Yield Fund-Reg(G)	0.0021	47	-0.29	0.7722	0.0193	0.0437	0.0022	0.0056	0.0596	44
11	Aditya Birla SL Dividend Yield Fund(G)	0.0001	45	0.0008	0.9994	0.0193	0.0412	0.0051	0.0048	0.0609	41

12	Cana ra Rob Emerg Equiti es Fund- Reg(G)	0.037 29 *	3	4.31 07	0	0.019 3	0.042 8	0.0063	0.032 8	0.1012	2
13	DSP Equity Oppor tunitie s Fund- Reg(G)	0.010 37	2 7	1.94 54	0.05 18	0.019 3	0.040 4	0.0005	0.008 9	0.0691	22
14	Kota k Equity Opp Fund(G)	0.009 47	2 9	1.90 16	0.05 73	0.019 3	0.040 4	0.0002	0.008 3	0.0682	25
15	Sund aram Large and Mid Cap Fund(G)	0.006 28	3 5	0.75	0.45 33	0.019 3	0.036	0.005	0.002 9	0.0631	34
16	Princ ipal Emerg ing Bluec hip Fund(G)	0.020 25 *	1 1	3.01 53	0.00 26	0.019 3	0.046 9	0.0048	0.017 7	0.0887	11
17	Frankl in India Equity	0.003 48	4 2	0.56 41	0.57 28	0.019 3	0.047 2	0.0015	0.001 2	0.0692	40

	Advan tage Fund (G)										
18	ICICI Pru Large & Mid Cap Fund(G)	- 0.003 2	4 8	- 0.42 4	0.67 16	0.019 3	0.044 7	0.003	- 0.006 6	0.0603	46
19	SBI Large & Midcap Fund-Reg(G)	0.003 74	4 1	0.62 97	0.52 89	0.019 3	0.047 8	0.0008	0.001 6	0.0695	38
20	UTI Core Equity Fund-Reg(G)	- 0.036 8	5 2	-1.29	0.19 72	0.019 3	0.016	0.0655	- 0.073	0.0278	52
21	Quant Large & Mid Cap Fund(G)	0.006 75	3 3	0.19 13	0.84 83	0.019 3	0.009 7	0.0838	- 0.046 5	0.0663	51
22	Mira Asset Large Cap Fund-Reg(G)	0.023 74 *	8	4.91 95	0	0.019 3	0.041 1	0	0.022 6	0.083	7

23	ICIC PruBluechip Fund(G)	0.01183 *	22	2.5403	0.0111	0.0193	0.0411	-0.0014	0.0108	0.0697	19
24	Aditya Birla SL Frontline Equity Fund (G)	0.01348 *	19	3.003	0.0027	0.0193	0.038	-0.0012	0.0126	0.0686	16
25	HDFC Top 100 Fund(G)	0.00643	34	1.042	0.2975	0.0193	0.0402	0.0042	0.0047	0.0684	31
26	Franklin India Bluechip Fund(G)	0.00604	36	1.3025	0.1929	0.0193	0.0409	-0.0032	0.0049	0.0618	29
27	HSBC Large Cap Equity Fund(G)	-0.0045	49	-0.851	0.395	0.0193	0.0373	-0.0004	-0.0057	0.0505	45
28	LIC MF Large Cap Fund(G)	-0.0048	50	-0.678	0.4978	0.0193	0.0395	0.0042	-0.0071	0.0559	47
29	DSP Midcap	0.0218 *	10	2.7631	0.0058	0.0193	0.0465	0.0025	0.0185	0.0867	9

	Fund-Reg(G)											
30	HDFC Mid-Cap Opportunities Fund(G)	0.03685 *	4	3.3991	0.0007	0.0193	0.0363	0.0068	0.0291	0.0915	4	
31	Kotak Emerging Equity Scheme(G)	0.01833 *	14	2.6416	0.0083	0.0193	0.0472	-0.0025	0.0155	0.0794	12	
32	Aditya Birla SL Midcap Fund(G)	0.87107	1	1.5572	0.1195	0.0193	0.0042	0.0455	0.0084	0.0773	23	
33	ICICI Pru Midcap Fund(G)	0.01076	25	1.4049	0.1602	0.0193	0.0521	0.0008	0.0069	0.0791	26	
34	Invesco India Midcap Fund(G)	0.02917 *	7	3.9056	0.0001	0.0193	0.046	-0.0017	0.0258	0.0893	6	
35	UTI Mid Cap	0.01225	21	1.8902	0.0589	0.0193	0.0551	0.0004	0.0096	0.0844	20	

	Fund-Reg(G)										
36	SBI Magnum Midcap Fund-Reg(G)	0.01004	28	1.1435	0.253	0.0193	0.0514	0.0061	0.0052	0.0819	28
37	Tata Mid Cap Growth Fund(G)	0.01723 *	15	2.3631	0.0182	0.0193	0.0471	-0.0004	0.0142	0.0802	14
38	Quant Mid Cap Fund(G)	0.00042	44	0.0408	0.9675	0.0193	0.0183	0.0144	-0.0143	0.0375	48
39	Taurus Discovery (Midcap) Fund-Reg (G)	0.00437	40	0.5669	0.5708	0.0193	0.0481	0.0053	0.0014	0.0741	39
40	Aditya Birla SL Small Cap Fund(G)	0.03044 *	6	4.1114	0	0.0193	0.0366	-0.0017	0.0275	0.0816	5
41	Franklin India Smalle	0.03517 *	5	4.4593	0	0.0193	0.0417	-0.0017	0.032	0.0913	3

	r Cos Fund(G)										
42	Kotak Small Cap Fund(G)	0.03805 *	2	4.0692	0	0.0193	0.0256	-0.0032	0.0357	0.0774	1
43	Quant Small Cap Fund(G)	0.0089	30	0.3645	0.7155	0.0193	0.0005	0.0481	-0.0349	0.033	50
44	ICICI Prusmallcap Fund(G)	0.01915 *	13	2.7371	0.0062	0.0193	0.0309	0.0021	0.012	0.0643	17
45	DSP Tax Saver Fund-Reg(G)	0.01529 *	17	3.0505	0.0023	0.0193	0.0407	-0.0003	0.014	0.0736	15
46	ICICI Pru LT Equity Fund (Tax Saving) (G)	0.02222 *	9	3.6532	0.0003	0.0193	0.0386	-0.0016	0.0202	0.0764	8
47	Principal Tax Savings Fund	0.00481	38	0.9122	0.3617	0.0193	0.0402	0.0035	0.0032	0.0661	33

48	Franklin India Taxshield(G)	0.01602 *	16	3.2189	0.0013	0.0193	0.0403	-0.0026	0.0147	0.0716	13
49	Kotak Tax Saver Scheme(G)	0.00324	43	0.7038	0.4816	0.0193	0.0412	0.0008	0.0022	0.0635	36
50	HDFC TaxSaver(G)	0.01079	24	1.5598	0.1189	0.0193	0.0384	0.0026	0.0084	0.0687	24
51	Quant Tax Plan(G)	0.00517	37	0.3606	0.7184	0.0193	0.0217	0.0164	-0.0049	0.0525	42
52	HDFC Capital Builder Value Fund(G)	0.02019 *	12	3.5235	0.0004	0.0193	0.0394	-0.0012	0.0184	0.0758	10
					Average		0.0193	0.0377	0.0071	0.0049	
					(in percentage)		27.80	54.49	10.36	7.34	100

Assessing Stock selectivity using Jensen Measure

Table 3. gives the results of Jensen measure of the selected mutual fund equity diversified growth schemes. A close examination of the Table reveals that 45 schemes have posted positive alpha values out of 52 equity diversified schemes considered in this study, which indicates that about 86% of fund managers out of the sampled schemes were able to beat the market by using their skill in the selection of the portfolio. This is an indication of the superior stock selection ability of equity fund managers. Best performing funds in terms of Jensen’s alpha during the study period are Aditya Birla SL Small Cap fund, Kotak Small Cap fund (Both from small-cap category) and Canara Robeco Emerging Equity fund (from the Large and Mid-cap fund category)

Out of the schemes with positive alpha values 20 schemes (38%) have generated a significantly positive alpha value at five percent level of significance. This is an evidence of portfolio manager's predictive ability to earn superior returns.

The schemes with significant positive value consists of two multi-cap funds (Franklin India Equity and HDFC Equity) , two Large and Mid-cap fund (Canara Robeco Emerging Equity and Principal Emerging Bluechip) and three Large-cap fund (Mirae Asset Large-cap, ICICI PruBluechip and Aditya Birla SL Frontline Equity), five Mid-cap fund (DSP Mid-cap, HDFC Mid-cap, Kotak Emerging Equity, Invesco India Midcap and Tata Mid-cap) and four Small-Cap fund (Aditya Birla SL Small cap, Franklin India Small-cap, Kotak Small-cap, ICICI Pru Small cap) and three ELSS schemes (DSP Tax saver, ICICI Pru Equity, Franklin India Tax Shield) and One Equity Value fund (HDFC Capital builder value fund) have successfully generated significantly positive alpha values at five percent level of significance. This indicates that the fund managers of these schemes have shown superior selectivity skills in India.

Assessing Fama's components to evaluate the performance of selected schemes

Results on Fama's decomposition measure have been placed in Table 3. The Fama model result shows that risk premium is positive for all the schemes. This means that all the 52 schemes considered in the study had provided positive performance on account of risk bearing activity of fund managers. Risk premium is found to be very high for the schemes compared to the other components of investment performance. In average, as expected risk premium is found to be very high (0.0377) (about 54.5%) and eats up a substantial portion of the actual average daily return earned by the scheme. This is mainly because of high systematic risk assumed by the schemes as represented by their beta values close to 1.

With regard to compensation for inadequate diversification 36 schemes (69%) out of 52 had shown positive performance.

After accounting for diversification, the residual performance on selectivity is attributed to net selectivity and it will be equal to (or less than) that on selectivity. A positive net selectivity will indicate superior performance. However, in case net selectivity is negative it would mean that the portfolio manager has not justified the loss of diversification.

In terms of net selectivity 40 schemes (77%) showed positive values indicating superior stock selection ability of the fund managers of these schemes and the rest 12 schemes (23%) have shown negative return. Kotak Small Cap Fund (Rank 1), Canara Robeco Emerging Equity (Rank 2) and Franklin India Smaller Cos Fund (Rank 3) are the top three schemes in the context of overall stock selection ability following Fama (1972).

Analysis of Jensen and Fama results It is important to report that all the schemes which have shown negative selectivity following Jensen criterion, have scored negative selectivity values following this measure also. In the selectivity analysis as per Jensen measure 7 schemes have shown negative returns. And as per net selectivity of Fama's measure of performance 12 schemes have shown negative performance. For the five schemes Aditya Birla SL Dividend Yield,

Quant Large & Mid Cap, Quant Mid Cap, Quant Small cap and Quant Tax plan though the overall selectivity scores are positive, their net selectivity scores turn to be negative. This means that these 5 funds have failed to generate enough returns to recover even a part of the compensation for the inadequate diversification of their portfolio. This suggests that these schemes could not justify the loss of diversification.

In this context, the results of Quant Small cap fund is worth to be mentioned separately. On the selectivity aspects, this scheme has earned a positive return of 0.0089 and ranked 30th. But due to very poor diversification ($R^2=0.00981$), compensation expected by the investors for the same is reported to be very high (0.04809). Hence, net selectivity of the scheme (-0.03486) becomes one of the worst schemes and contributed enough to bring down the rank of the scheme to 50.

Thus 39 schemes out of 52 schemes considered in the study, which had reported positive net selectivity seem to be more reliable as far as the professional skill of the managers is concerned during the study period. On an average there is a positive net selectivity of 0.00492.

4. Conclusion

The present study has evaluated the performance of Indian equity diversified mutual fund schemes in terms of return and risk and diversification. Study also assessed the stock selection ability by applying the measures such as Jensen and Fama. The analysis of average return indicated that all the schemes were able to earn a positive return greater than the average risk free rate of return. About 65% of the mutual fund schemes outperformed the market. Beta values revealed that schemes were relatively exposed to less risk than the market as all the schemes under study except one have a beta value less than one. But beta values greater than 0.8 indicated a high degree of volatility. A majority of the funds were reasonably diversified. Empirical evidence also suggests that fund managers of some of the sample mutual fund schemes were engaged in micro forecasting (or stock selection) as the alpha values in case of 20 schemes (38%) were positive and statistically significant at five percent level. This is an evidence of portfolio manager's predictive ability to earn superior returns. 40 out of 52 (i.e about 77%) schemes had reported positive net selectivity which indicates professional skill of the managers. We can therefore say that Indian mutual fund industry has been able to add value to its investors wealth through its stock selectivity ability. It still has the potential to outperform the market.

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